

Questioning the Readiness of Local Residents in Managing Community-Based Tourism? A Case in Pulisan Village, North Minahasa Regency, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Community based tourism is a tourism management concept where the local community as the owner of tourism potential, is involved in tourism management. It requires a strong commitment from the community to be directly involved in it. Pulisan is the name of the village in Likupang which is the centre of the development of the Special Economic Zone for tourism. In the last five years it has received tourism development assistance ranging from physical infrastructure to hospitality skills training. However, from several observations in the field, it was found that the reactivity of the community in implementing the various benefits that had been distributed to the community was in-effective. The purpose of this study is to examine the readiness of local communities in managing community-based tourism. Descriptive research is the approach to solve this case. Then the data collection technique through a survey of 81 respondents who live in that village. While the analytical tool used is a Likert scale. The results found that for the three main indicators, namely attractions, amenity and accessibility, the average respondent's answer was willing, while for the supporting components, respondents were still undecided.

KEYWORDS: local residents, ready, managing community-based tourism, pulisan village

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the industries that can drive the regional economy and improve the welfare of the local community, (Gnanapala, & Sandaruwani, 2016). By developing the potential of tourist objects and attractions that are packaged in a product that has selling value and competitiveness, it will be able to attract tourists to visit a tourist destination. The tourism industry produces products and services, both of which are simultaneously enjoyed by tourists. Products in this case are tourist attractions while services are services, (Towoliu, et.al, 2017).

Tourism in developing countries such as Indonesia, is growing so fast, this is also because of tourism can provide significant economic income. People from various social strata even if they do not have adequate knowledge, and sufficient financial resources are considered to be able to contribute to it, ((Prasetyo, & Suryoko, 2018; Yanes et al., 2019; Arintoko, et.al, 2020). Therefore, tourism is used as a tool to solve the problem of improving welfare in rural communities, (Petrović et. al, 2017). Almost all villages in Indonesia prioritize tourism as a superior program for village development. This approach pattern also synergizes with the Indonesian central government policy which makes tourism a leading sector. The impact is that all sectors in state management institutions are required to support tourism. This paradigm of approach is also in line at the local government level; vertical from the government to all levels below including village governments.

In recent years, the Government of Indonesia has provided various stimuli for tourism development in the regions. One of the tourism development strategy models is to form a strategic tourism area in several selected destinations with the main target as a development trigger for the area. Currently there are 8 strategic tourism areas in Indonesia, (Wenas, et.al, 2023). In developing these areas, the central government has built various supporting infrastructure such as expanding road and bridge access. In addition, it provides housing assistance to local communities to serve as homestays. Do not forget also with various complementary amenities as a residence for tourists who will visit the area. This acceleration is also carried out by working with several educational institutions that hold tourism programs to help train local communities, especially in the field of hospitality. The amount of assistance provided by the government to local communities, with the hope that they will develop and participate in the management and development of tourism in the village where the location of the special economic tourism area is located. Community participation in tourism development is known as CBT.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The applying of tourism development model, it involves more active participation from local communities. CBT is tourism that involves local communities by providing opportunities to manage and develop tourism, either directly or indirectly that has links with industry or tourism businesses, so that the distribution of profits is evenly distributed to communities in rural / coastal areas and small islands, (Putra, 2015).

In essence, tourism development cannot be separated from the resources and uniqueness of the local community, both in the form of physical and non-physical elements (tradition and culture), which are the main driving elements of tourism activities themselves, (Sunaryo, 2013; Towoliu, et.al, 2023), community-based tourism activities, namely: (a) tourism management that provides opportunities for local communities to control and be actively involved in the management and development of existing tourism, (b) then tourism management that can provide opportunities for people who are directly involved in the business. - Tourism businesses can also benefit from existing tourism and (c) a tourism model that demands systematic and democratic empowerment and a fair distribution of benefits to disadvantaged communities in the destination, (Hayat, et.al, 2018). Community-based tourism is closely related to the certainty of active participation of the local community in tourism development. Community participation in tourism consists of two perspectives, namely community participation in the decision-making process and participation related to the distribution of benefits received by the community from tourism development. Therefore, basically there are three main principles in the planning strategy of community-based tourism development or community-based tourism, namely: (1) Involving community members in decision making, (2) There is certainty that local communities will receive benefits from tourism activities, and (3) tourism education for local communities, (Sunaryo, 2013).

The principles of CBT that must be carried out are: (1) recognizing, supporting and promoting community ownership in tourism, (2) involving community members from every stage of tourism development in various aspects, (3) promoting pride in the community concerned, (4) increasing quality of life, (5) ensuring environmental sustainability, (6) protecting the characteristics (uniqueness) and culture of local communities, (7) developing cross-cultural learning, (8) respecting cultural differences and human dignity (9) distributing benefits and benefits obtained proportionately to community members, (10) contributing a certain percentage of the income earned for community development, and (11) highlighting the authenticity of the community's relationship with its environment, (Hayat, et.al, 2018). From some of these opinions, CBT is very different from the development of tourism in general (mass tourism). In CBT, the community is the main actor in the process of tourism development, with the main goal of improving people's living standards. So, it can be concluded that CBT is a tourism model that is owned by the community and managed by the community with the intention of providing broad benefits to the community, (Manyara, & Jones, 2007; Okazaki, 2008; Goodwin, & Santilli, 2009). Some of the advantages that can be obtained from CBT such as recognition of benefits obtained, expression of purpose, involvement of stakeholders, involvement of leaders, and effectiveness of decision implementation, (Kibicho, 2008). Similarly, (Armstrong, 2012) states that CBT provides strong community attachment, genuine participation of the community, ownership control, commercial planning, attractive and quality products, transparent financial management, stakeholder support and effective evaluation. Meanwhile CBT provides implications in its application such as: economics, social, cultural, environmental and political, (Darmayanti, & Oka, (2020).

Pulisan Village, located in the East Likupang sub-district of North Minahasa district, has natural beauty that is currently in the process of tourism development, (Towoliu, et.al, 2018). There are mangrove forests and coral reefs that attract tourists to do tourism activities such as exploring mangrove forests, canoeing, snorkelling and diving. In addition, Pulisan Village also has interesting historical, artistic and cultural values to support tourism activities. Since being designated as a Special Economic Zone for Tourism, Pulisan Village and its surroundings have continued to improve, with special assistance for tourism supporting facilities and infrastructure. The current problem is that the community's knowledge about tourism and how to manage existing potential is still very low. Tourism requires the readiness of the local community to accept changes that occur both from the physical environment, but also the human resources in the village, to be able to accept and manage existing tourism activities. The purpose of this study is to examine the preparation of community readiness in managing community-based tourism.

III. METHOD

In this study, using a qualitative method approach. The qualitative method is to obtain data from certain natural (not artificial) places, but researchers carry out treatments in collecting data, by distributing questionnaires, (Nuraeni, & Suryawardani, 2017); Hollstein, 2011). This research is aimed at solving problems, where this method is not only limited to collecting and compiling data from various existing facts, but looking at analysis and interpretation of the meaning of the data, through research conducted on the natural and social environment, (Kusmayadi dan Endar, 2000). Sampling in this study was through probability sampling, namely proportionate stratified random sampling. Probability sampling is a sampling technique that provides equal opportunities for everyone elements (members) of the population to be selected as sample members (Sugiyono, dan Endar, 2000). The size of the sample in this study was determined by the Slovin formula as follows: The formula $n = N/(1 + Ne^2)$.

where:

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n = number of elements / sample members

N = number of elements / members of the population

e = error level (error level) (note: generally used 1% or 0.01, 5% or 0.05, and 10% or 0.1) (notes can be selected by the researcher).

To limit the scope of the research problem, operationally what is measured in community readiness in tourism management is the readiness of human resources mentally and physically for changes that will be carried out in a planned manner by the developer, where the community is voluntarily willing to be involved in planning and tourism activities. The tourism development in question is related to the tourism offering components including: (1) attractions, (2) accessibility, (3) amenities and (4) ancillary. Then the data collection technique was carried out through surveys by distributing questionnaires to local communities and observing community activities related to the data needed in the study. While the analytical tool used is the Likert scale, with indicators presented proportionally, namely (1) Very Unprepared [SNR], 2 Not Ready [NR], 3 Neutral [N], 4 Ready (R) and 5 Very Ready (SR), (Alismail, & Zhang, 2020).

IV. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Based on the Slovin formula with a population of 420 people, the sample size for data collection through a survey is 80.76 respondents which are rounded up to 81 respondents. The following is the respondent's data taken by researchers using a survey method of 81 who live in Pulisan Village. The characteristics of the respondents taken consisted of gender, age and education level.

Based on the gender data of 81 respondents, the data obtained were 53.3% male and 45.7% female. The data shows that the number of respondents is almost evenly distributed based on gender. The probability sampling technique explains that sampling like this will provide equal opportunities for each element (member) of the population to be selected as a member of the sample, (Sugiyono, 2010). Then based on the age group where the results are: age 21 to 30 years amounted to 32.1%; 31 s / d 40 years amounted to 24.7%; 41 to 50 years old amounted to 30.9% and over 51 years amounted to 12.3%. The data shows that the percentage of such age indicates the potential age to work in the tourism industry. Furthermore, the education level of the respondents, the results show that: Elementary School (SD) 29.6%, Junior High School (SMP) 28.4%, High School (SMU/SMK) 39.5% and Higher Education or Bachelor's Degree 2.5%. Please note that the level of education is very influential on the contribution of employment in certain fields in the Tourism Industry. By looking at the composition of elementary and junior high school education, it will certainly affect the choice or level of work in the tourism industry.

The planning for the development of a special tourism economic area in Tanjung Pulisan greatly affects the lives of the people who live in Pulisan Village. The involvement of local communities in a tourism area to be built is very much needed with the smooth development process. The following are the results of community respondents' answers to the community's willingness to change needed in the development of Community-Based Tourism (CBT). These changes are associated with the components of offering tourist destinations, including: attraction, accessibility, amenities and ancillary.

In table 1 it is clear that the results of respondents' answers related to the readiness of local communities in Community-Based Tourism Development (CBT).

Table 1. Local Residents Readiness in Community-Based Tourism management

No	Indicators	Mean	Sd
A.	Attraction		
1	The natural potential around the place of residence is used as a tourist attraction	4.5802	0.49659
2	Forests, beaches, rivers, waterfalls or even plantations are used as tourist attractions	4.5802	0.49659
3	Regional songs, cultural dances, regional literature, village traditions or other local wisdom are used as tourist attractions	4.4074	0.70317
4	Livelihoods such as farmers/fishers are used as tourist attractions	4.4815	0.63465
5	Involved in the planning and arrangement of attractions	4.4321	0.77360
B	Amenities		
6	The area around the house is built for tourist facilities.	4.1605	0.88680
7	The area in the house (room/toilet) is rearranged for the benefit of tourists	4.1111	0.97468
8	Providing clean water for guest needs	4.3580	0.69478
9	Providing clean food to guests	4.7037	0.51099
10	Keeping the home environment clean	4.7037	0.45947
C	Accessibility		
11	The area in front of the house is made of a road for tourism purposes	4.3827	0.69943
12	Ensure safety for visitors who come to tourist sites	4.6049	0.54035

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13	Making guests feel comfortable in their activities at tourist sites	4.6296	0.53489
14	Give directions to visitors when they get lost while on location.	4.5802	0.49659
D	Ancillary		
15	Trained as a tour guide	3.5185	0.89598
16	Trained as a receptionist	3.6914	0.93062
17	Trained coast guard or tourism task force	3.3086	0.97008
18	Trained or added skills in the field of cooking	3.5432	1.17313
19	Trained in foreign language skills (English/Chinese)	4.4568	0.72542

Source: researcher processed data.

Based on the results of respondents' answers to their readiness in managing community tourism, it can be seen from the four components of the tourism offer. It is clear where from 4A, 3 main components, namely Attraction, Amenities and Accessibility, respondents' answers agree or are willing to manage tourism. Of the five questions, the average of those who answered readiness in tourist attractions was 4.49628, meaning that it was close to 5.0 or very willing. This can be interpreted that the local community is very enthusiastic about accepting change and is willing to be involved in managing community-based tourism attractions.

Next for questions related to community readiness related to amenities for tourism. Completeness required for the needs of tourist facilities can be seen from the five questions, the average respondent answered willingly 4.4074. Close to 5.0 or very willing. This means the same enthusiasm when there are changes and the provision of various basic needs for tourism purposes. The local community gladly agreed.

Then for questions related to tourism accessibility, road construction and guarantees for the security and safety of visitors while at tourist sites. It can be seen that from the four questions, the average respondent answered yes, which was 4.5507. This means that the local community remains consistently enthusiastic about ensuring comfort for guests visiting and being at tourist sites.

However, it is inversely related to the ancillary component. Questions related to additional technical skills, to complement the needs related to skills in tourism. Practically, respondents answered doubtfully, as seen from the five questions given, the average respondent answered undecided, 3.7037. Even though these questions will open up opportunities for them to be given skills related to the tourism industry. Of the five questions, practically only 1 question was approved, namely additional foreign language proficiency (English & Chinese). This phenomenon is interesting considering that additional needs, such as being given cooking skills training, and tour guides, do not seem to be very popular. Though these skills are needed in tourism management.

From these results and compared with the implications of community-based tourism, it can be concluded as follows: (1) The economic dimension, where the community has the confidence to manage the overall resources of tourist attractions in the village. Thus, the local community in the next few years will benefit economically from the development of village tourism and significantly fulfil the needs of themselves and their families. (2) Social dimension, local communities are actively involved in tourism development so as to improve their quality of life. Where they are willing to give part of the land to be used as access and try to jointly maintain village security. Effective interaction occurs between community members in daily life. The contribution of the community's role in the development of tourism villages will create a comfortable atmosphere for visitors and tourists. (3) In the cultural dimension, villagers endeavor to preserve their art and culture so that it remains sustainable. This can be seen in the desire for dances, folk songs and other local wisdom in the village. (4) The environmental dimension, the willingness of the community to participate in environmental hygiene programs in order to maintain and care for the environment because a clean and comfortable village is one of the important aspects in the management of a tourist village. They realize that preserving the environment can attract tourists to visit the village. (5) The political dimension, where the management of tourist villages has prioritized local communities as labor, as well as guaranteeing their rights in the management of tourist villages. Thus, it can be stated that the willingness of the community in Pulisan Village has shown that the concept of community-based tourism by involving the active participation of the community in the development of tourist villages will be successful, considering that they are the owners of the village who really understand the existence of their village.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the management of community-based tourism, the full involvement of the community is needed. Unlike in mass tourism-based tourism, where people are only left like spectators, receiving benefits from tourism business organizers. The community does not feel ownership of tourist activities, even though they have these attractions. Communities are left, and almost at some point fooled, from a number of benefits obtained by tourism operators. The case from Pulisan Village illustrates that with enthusiasm the community is willing to accept change, wholeheartedly wants to be involved in managing tourism. The average community is willing to manage community-based tourism, it can be seen from the results of research conducted, although on the other hand there are still doubts related to the skills needed in tourism management. More time is needed to convince local communities that community-based tourism must also be equipped with hospitality skills. In conclusion, CBT has had good implications for the

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community, they feel valued and involved in the management and development of their village.

Finally, this research is limited to community readiness in community-based tourism management, it is hoped that in the next study for researchers who will continue, it is advisable to produce a model or system of community-based tourist destination management.

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